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Appendices

Appendix A

Personality-Related Questions

Please respond to the following statements according to your experience.

There are no right or wrong answers - the important thing is to answer honestly..

Questions P1

Question 1.1

How do you rate yourself in terms of your programming experience compared to your fellow students?

very inexperienced						very experi- enced
<input type="checkbox"/>						

Question 1.2

How experienced are you with the logical programming paradigm?

very inexperienced						very experi- enced
<input type="checkbox"/>						

Question 1.3

How would you rate yourself in terms of your programming experience with the Python programming language?

very
inexperienced

very experi-
enced

Question P2

Question

Which other programming languages do you consider yourself to have at least an intermediate level of proficiency in?

If it is more than 3, please specify only your 3 most familiar languages then add only the number of the remaining languages.

Appendix B

Item Pool

Item Fr1x1

Type: Bound Format: Multiple Choice with Justification

Ability to be tested: analytical skills and ability to abstract

Task

Please justify in 1-3 sentences why your answer is correct and why the others are not. You will only get a point for the answer and the justification.

```
1 def process_data(data):
2     result = [0] * len(data)
3     for i in range(len(data)):
4         if i % 2 == 0:
5             result[i] = data[i] * 2
6         else:
7             result[i] = data[i] - 1
8     final_value = 0
9     for value in result:
10        final_value += value
11    return final_value
12
13
14 data_input = [3, 7, 2, 8, 5]
15 output = process_data(data_input)
16 print("Output:", output)
```

Options:

Select all that apply

- a) It doubles the even-indexed elements of the list and decreases the odd-indexed elements by 1, then returns the sum of the modified list.
- b) It creates a new list where even-indexed elements are doubled and odd-

- indexed elements are decreased by one, then returns the modified list.
- c) It modifies the input list by multiplying elements at even indices by 2 and subtracting 1 from odd-indexed elements, then calculates and returns the sum of that list.

Justification:

Correct Answer: a)

Possible Justification:

a) "It doubles the even-indexed elements of the list and decreases the odd-indexed elements by 1, then returns the sum of the modified list."

Evaluation Scheme: binary scoring

Answer	Points
Wrong answer with wrong or without justification	0
Wrong answer with right justification	0
Correct answer with wrong or without justification	0
Correct answer with plausible justification	1

Item Fr1x2

Type: Bound Format: Multiple Choice with Justification

Ability to be tested: ability to abstract

Task

How does the code behave if the input list `data_input` is empty?
Please justify in 1-3 sentences why your answer is correct and why the others are not. You will only get a point for the answer and the justification.

The code is the same as the code for task 1.1.

```

1 def process_data(data):
2     result = [0] * len(data)
3     for i in range(len(data)):
4         if i % 2 == 0:
5             result[i] = data[i] * 2
6         else:
7             result[i] = data[i] - 1
8     final_value = 0
9     for value in result:
10        final_value += value
11    return final_value
12
13
14 data_input = [3, 7, 2, 8, 5]
15 output = process_data(data_input)
16 print("Output:", output)

```

Options:

Select all that apply

- a) The code returns an error message.
- b) The code returns 0.
- c) The code returns None.

Justification:

Correct Answer: b)

Possible Justification:

b) "The code returns 0 when the input list is empty because no iterations occur, and the initialized final_value of 0 is returned unchanged."

Evaluation Scheme: binary scoring

Answer	Points
Wrong answer with wrong or without justification	0
Wrong answer with right justification	0
Correct answer with wrong or without justification	0
Correct answer with plausible justification	1

Item Fr1x3

Type: Bound Format: dichotomous task

Ability to be tested: analytical skills and ability to abstract

Task

Please select the flowchart that reflects the code.
Please justify in 1-3 sentences why your answer is correct and why the others are not. You will only get a point for the answer and the justification.

The code is the same as the code for task 1.1.

```
1 def process_data(data):
2     result = [0] * len(data)
3     for i in range(len(data)):
4         if i % 2 == 0:
5             result[i] = data[i] * 2
6         else:
7             result[i] = data[i] - 1
8     final_value = 0
9     for value in result:
10        final_value += value
11    return final_value
12
13
14 data_input = [3, 7, 2, 8, 5]
15 output = process_data(data_input)
16 print("Output:", output)
```

A flowchart for code is a visual representation of a program's logic, structure, and flow. It illustrates how a program processes input, performs operations, makes decisions, and produces output. It uses standardized symbols to represent various programming constructs like loops, conditions, and functions.

Options:

Choose one of the following answers

Flowchart 1
Flowchart 2

Justification:

Correct Answer: Flowchart 2

Possible Justification:

“Flowchart 2 is correct because it applies the condition if $i \% 2 == 0$ to double the even-indexed values and subtract 1 from the odd-indexed values, which matches the code. Flowchart 1 is incorrect because it swaps the actions for the even and odd cases.”

Evaluation Scheme: binary scoring

Answer	Points
Wrong answer with wrong or without justification	0
Wrong answer with right justification	0
Correct answer with wrong or without justification	0
Correct answer with plausible justification	1

Item Fr2x1

Type: Bound Format: Multiple Choice with Justification

Ability to be tested: analytical skills and ability to abstract

Task

What is the output of the following code? Please justify in 1-3 sentences why your answer is correct and why the others are not. You will only get a point for the answer and the justification.

```
1 def generate_string(numbers):
2     result = ""
3     i = 1
4     while i < len(numbers) - 1:
5         i += 1
6         if numbers[i] % 2 != 0:
7             result += "A"
8         else:
9             result += "B"
10            result += "C"
11    return result
12
13 numbers = [4, 7, 2, 5, 8, 4, 9]
14 output = generate_string(numbers)
15 print("Output:", output)
```

Options:

Select all that apply

- a) BCACBCBCAC
- b) BCBCACBCAC
- c) CACBCACBC

Justification:

Correct Answer: a)

Possible Justification:

a) "The loop starts at $i = 1$ and increments i by 1, so it processes elements starting from `numbers[2]` (index 2). The numbers processed are 2 (even), 5 (odd), 8 (even), 4 (even), and 9 (odd)." Even numbers result in the addition of "B" and odd numbers in the addition of

"A". After every loop a "C" is added."

Evaluation Scheme: binary scoring

Answer	Points
Wrong answer with wrong or without justification	0
Wrong answer with right justification	0
Correct answer with wrong or without justification	0
Correct answer with plausible justification	1

Item Fr2x2

Type: Bound Format: Matching task

Ability to be tested: analytical skills and ability to abstract

Task

Please assign the following inputs to their corresponding outputs.
Please justify in 1-3 sentences why your answer is correct. You can only get one point, when everything is assigned correctly and justified.

The code is the same as the code for task 2.1.

```
1 def generate_string(numbers):
2     result = ""
3     i = 1
4     while i < len(numbers) - 1:
5         i += 1
6         if numbers[i] % 2 != 0:
7             result += "A"
8         else:
9             result += "B"
10            result += "C"
11    return result
12
13 numbers = [4, 7, 2, 5, 8, 4, 9]
14 output = generate_string(numbers)
15 print("Output:", output)
```

Inputs	Outputs
A = [4, 7, 2, 5, 8, 4]	1 = "BCACACBC"
B = [6, 3, 5, 8, 2, 4]	2 = "ACACBCBC"
C = [7, 9, 1, 3, 8, 6]	3 = "BCACBCBC"
D = [3, 6, 2, 1, 7, 8]	4 = "ACBCBCBC"

Justification:

Correct Answer:

A = 3
 B = 4
 C = 2
 D = 1

Possible Justification:

a) "The loop starts at $i = 1$ and increments i by 1, so it processes elements starting from numbers[2] (index 2). The numbers processed are 2 (even), 5 (odd), 8 (even), 4 (even), and 9 (odd)." Even numbers result in the addition of "B" and odd numbers in the addition of "A". After every loop a "C" is added."

Evaluation Scheme: binary scoring

Answer	Points
Wrong answer with wrong or without justification	0
Wrong answer with right justification	0
Correct answer with wrong or without justification	0
Correct answer with plausible justification	1

Item Fr2x3

Type: Bound Format: Multiple Choice with Justification

Ability to be tested: analytical skills and ability to abstract

Task

Which of the following statements about the function is/are true?
Please justify in 1-3 sentences why your answer is correct and why the others are not. You will only get a point for the answer and the justification.

The code is the same as the code for task 2.1.

```
1 def generate_string(numbers):
2     result = ""
3     i = 1
4     while i < len(numbers) - 1:
5         i += 1
6         if numbers[i] % 2 != 0:
7             result += "A"
8         else:
9             result += "B"
10            result += "C"
11    return result
12
13 numbers = [4, 7, 2, 5, 8, 4, 9]
14 output = generate_string(numbers)
15 print("Output:", output)
```

Options:

Select all that apply

- a) The function processes all elements in the input list.
- b) The function always adds the same number of "C" characters as there are numbers in the input list.
- c) The function skips the first element and only processes numbers starting from the second element.
- d) The function correctly handles an input list with fewer than three elements by returning an empty string.

Justification:

Correct Answer: c) / d)

Possible Justification:

c) "The function skips the first element and only processes numbers starting from the second element."

d) "The function correctly handles an input list with fewer than three elements by returning an empty string."

Evaluation Scheme: binary scoring

Answer	Points
Wrong answer with wrong or without justification	0
Wrong answer with right justification	0
Correct answer with wrong or without justification	0
Correct answer with plausible justification	1

Item Fr3x1

Type: Free Format: Short essay

Ability to be tested: analytical skills and ability to abstract

Task

Give the method a meaningful name that more clearly describes what it does.

Please justify your answer in 1-3 sentences. You will only get a point for the answer and the justification.

```
1 def process_input(v):
2     i = 0
3     j = len(v) - 1
4
5     while i < j:
6         if v[i] < v[j]:
7             v[j] = v[j] - v[i]
8         elif v[i] > v[j]:
9             v[i] = v[i] - v[j]
10        else:
11            i = i + 1
12    return v
```

Name:

Justification:

Correct Answer:

“reduceArrayValues”
“iterativeValueReduction”
“convergeArrayEnds”
“pairwiseValueAdjustment”
“equalizeArrayEnds”

Possible Justification:

“The method repeatedly compares the values at the two ends of the array and reduces the larger one by the smaller until they converge or become equal, which explains names like “reduceArrayValues” or “equalizeArrayEnds.”

Evaluation Scheme: binary scoring

Answer	Points
Wrong answer with wrong or without justification	0
Wrong answer with right justification	0
Correct answer with wrong or without justification	0
Correct answer with plausible justification	1

Item Fr3x2

Type: Bound Format: Multiple Choice with Justification

Ability to be tested: analytical skills, ability to abstract and critical thinking

Task

Which of the tests uncovers an issue in the source code?
Please justify in 1-3 sentences why your answer is correct and why the others are not. You will only get a point for the answer and the justification.

The code is the same as the code for task 3.1.

```

1 def process_input(v):
2     i = 0
3     j = len(v) - 1
4
5     while i < j:
6         if v[i] < v[j]:
7             v[j] = v[j] - v[i]
8         elif v[i] > v[j]:
9             v[i] = v[i] - v[j]
10        else:
11            i = i + 1
12    return v

```

Options:

Select all that apply

- a) Input: v = [14, 1, 42]
- b) Input: v = [1, 0, 18]
- c) Input: v = [1, 13, 1]

Justification:

Correct Answer: b)

Possible Justification:

b) "b, because 0 is not processed."

Evaluation Scheme: binary scoring

Answer	Points
Wrong answer with wrong or without justification	0
Wrong answer with right justification	0
Correct answer with wrong or without justification	0
Correct answer with plausible justification	1

Item Fr4x1

Type: Bound Format: Multiple Choice with Justification

Ability to be tested: analytical skills, ability to abstract and critical thinking

Task

Which of the three code snippets fulfills the following specification?

The function should replace all negative numbers in a list with the value 0. All positive numbers and 0 remain unchanged.

Please justify in 1-3 sentences why your answer is correct and why the others are not. You will only get a point for the answer and the justification.

```
1 #Snippet 1
2 def replace_negatives_v1(lst):
3     for i in range(len(lst)):
4         if lst[i] < 0:
5             lst[i] = 0
6     return lst
7
8
9 #Snippet 2
10 def replace_negatives_v2(lst):
11     result = [0] * len(lst)
12     for i in range(len(lst)):
13         if lst[i] < 0:
14             result[i] = 0
15         else:
16             result[i] = lst[i]
17     return result
18
19
20 #Snippet 3
21 def replace_negatives_v3(lst):
22     for i in range(len(lst)):
23         if lst[i] > 0:
24             lst[i] = lst[i] + 1
25     return lst
```

Options:

Select all that apply

- a) Snippet 1
- b) Snippet 2
- c) Snippet 3

Justification:

Correct Answer: Snippet 1 & Snippet 2

Possible Justification:

a) "Snippet 1: This function goes through each element of the list and replaces it with 0 if it is negative. It fulfills the specification because all negative numbers are replaced by 0 and all other numbers remain unchanged."

"Snippet 2: Here, too, negative numbers are replaced by 0, which meets the specification."

"Snippet 3: In this version, only the positive numbers are changed by incrementing them by 1. It does not correspond to the specification, as only positive numbers are changed and not the negative ones, as required in the specification."

Evaluation Scheme: binary scoring

Answer	Points
Wrong answer with wrong or without justification	0
Wrong answer with right justification	0
Correct answer with wrong or without justification	0
Correct answer with plausible justification	1

Item Fr5x1

Type: Bound Format: Multiple Choice with Justification

Ability to be tested: analytical skills, ability to abstract and critical thinking

Task

The code is supposed to do the following:

Calculate the largest difference between consecutive numbers in a list.

Does it fulfill this function?

Please justify in 1-3 sentences why your answer is correct and why the others are not. You will only get a point for the answer and the justification.

```
1 def max(numbers):
2     m = 0
3     total_elements = len(numbers)
4
5     for i in range(total_elements - 1):
6         d = numbers[i + 1] - numbers[i]
7         for j in range(1):
8             temp_d = d * 1
9             if d > m:
10                m = d
11            elif d < 0:
12                m = d
13        return m
14
15 numbers = [1, 5, 3, 9, 2]
16 output = max(numbers)
17 print("Max difference:", output)
```

Options:

Choose one of the following answers

- a) Yes, it does.
- b) No, it does not.

Justification:

Correct Answer: b)

Possible Justification:

a) "No, the code does not fulfill its intended function because it incorrectly sets `max_diff` to negative differences, which leads to an incorrect result."

Evaluation Scheme: binary scoring

Answer	Points
Wrong answer with wrong or without justification	0
Wrong answer with right justification	0
Correct answer with wrong or without justification	0
Correct answer with plausible justification	1

Item Fr5x2

Type: Free Format: short essay

Ability to be tested: critical thinking

Task

How would you evaluate the efficiency and readability of the code?

The code is the same as the code for task 5.1.

```
1 def max(numbers):
2     m = 0
3     total_elements = len(numbers)
4
5     for i in range(total_elements - 1):
6         d = numbers[i + 1] - numbers[i]
7         for j in range(1):
8             temp_d = d * 1
9             if d > m:
10                m = d
11            elif d < 0:
12                m = d
13        return m
14
15 numbers = [1, 5, 3, 9, 2]
16 output = max(numbers)
17 print("Max difference:", output)
```

Evaluation:

Possible evaluation:

"The code is inefficient due to unnecessary calculations, which slow down the process. The code is harder to read due to unnecessary operations as well as inadequate or inappropriate variable names. Additionally, it contains a logical error in handling negative differences. Furthermore, it contains a logical error in handling negative differences. *Also no comments were used (optional).*"

Evaluation Scheme: partial credit scoring

Answer	Points
Incorrect or none of the mentioned issues	0
Some but not all of the mentioned issues	1
All of the mentioned issues	2

Item Fr5x3

Type: Free Format: short essay

Ability to be tested: critical thinking

Task

How could the code be improved regarding its readability and efficiency?

The code is the same as the code for task 5.1.

```
1 def max(numbers):
2     m = 0
3     total_elements = len(numbers)
4
5     for i in range(total_elements - 1):
6         d = numbers[i + 1] - numbers[i]
7         for j in range(1):
8             temp_d = d * 1
9             if d > m:
10                m = d
11            elif d < 0:
12                m = d
13        return m
14
15 numbers = [1, 5, 3, 9, 2]
16 output = max(numbers)
17 print("Max difference:", output)
```

Evaluation:

Possible evaluation:

"It would benefit from a clearer and more concise structure, eliminating unnecessary steps. Variables should be given descriptive and meaningful names. *The logical error of incorrectly setting `max_diff` to negative difference in line 12 should be corrected and the use of comments could improve the readability (optional).*"

Evaluation Scheme: partial credit scoring

Answer	Points
Incorrect or none of the mentioned issues	0
Some but not all of the mentioned issues	1
All of the mentioned issues	2

Appendix C

Debriefing Questions

Please respond to the following statements according to your experience. There are no right or wrong answers - the important thing is to answer honestly and spontaneously.

Question D1

Question					
The task was clear and unambiguous.					
Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Task started	not
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Disruptive Factor to be identified: Unclear or incomplete instructions

Question D2

Question					
The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.					
Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Task started	not
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Disruptive Factor to be identified: Mismatch between task difficulty and skill level

Question D3

Question					
I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.					
Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Task not started	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Disruptive Factor to be identified: Time

Question D4

Question
Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
Yes, I did.
No, I did not.
What was the problem?
<input type="text"/>

Disruptive Factor to be identified: Technical difficulties (hardware/software/network issues)

Appendix D

Figures

D.1 Personality-Related Questions

Question P1.2

How experienced are you with the logical programming paradigm?

Question P1.3

How would you rate yourself in terms of your programming experience with the Python programming language?

Question P2

Which other programming languages do you consider yourself to have at least an intermediate level of proficiency in? If it is more than 3, please specify only your 3 most familiar languages and the number of the remaining languages.

D.2 Tasks with Debriefing

Fr1x1

DeFr1x1.1
The task was clear and unambiguous.

DeFr1x1.2
The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.

DeFr1x1.3
I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.

DeTe1x1

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
What was the problem?

Fr1x2

DeFr1x2.1

The task was clear and unambiguous.

DeFr1x2.2

The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.

DeFr1x2.3

I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.

DeTe1x2

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
What was the problem?

Fr1x3

DeFr1x3.1

The task was clear and unambiguous.

DeFr1x3.2

The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.

DeFr1x3.3

I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.

DeTe1x3

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
What was the problem?

Fr2x1

DeFr2x1.1

The task was clear and unambiguous.

DeFr2x1.2

The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.

DeFr2x1.3

I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.

DeTe2x1

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
What was the problem?

Fr2x2

DeFr2x2.1

The task was clear and unambiguous.

DeFr2x2.2

The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.

DeFr2x2.3

I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.

DeTe1x3

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
What was the problem?

no problems (31) other problems (3)
problem not mentioned (1) actual technical problem (0)

Fr2x3

DeFr2x3.1

The task was clear and unambiguous.

DeFr2x3.2

The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.

DeFr2x3.3

I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.

DeTe1x3

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
What was the problem?

no problems (31) other problems (0)
problem not mentioned (4) actual technical problem (0)

Fr3x1

DeFr3x1.1

The task was clear and unambiguous.

DeFr3x1.2

The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.

DeFr3x1.3

I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.

DeTe2x1

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
What was the problem?

Fr3x2

DeFr3x2.1

The task was clear and unambiguous.

DeFr3x2.2

The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.

DeFr3x2.3

I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.

DeTe1x3

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
What was the problem?

Fr4x1

DeFr4x1.1

The task was clear and unambiguous.

DeFr4x1.2

The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.

DeFr4x1.3

I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.

DeTe2x1

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
What was the problem?

■ no problems (30) ■ other problems (1)
■ problem not mentioned (2) ■ actual technical problem (0)

Fr5x1

DeFr5x1.1

The task was clear and unambiguous.

DeFr5x1.2

The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.

DeFr5x1.3

I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.

DeTe2x1

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
What was the problem?

Fr5x2

DeFr5x2.1

The task was clear and unambiguous.

DeFr5x2.2

The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.

DeFr5x2.3

I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.

DeTe1x3

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
What was the problem?

Fr5x3

DeFr5x3.1

The task was clear and unambiguous.

DeFr5x3.2

The difficulty level of the task matched my skill and experience.

DeFr5x3.3

I felt I had sufficient time to complete the task without feeling rushed.

DeTe1x3

Did you experience any technical difficulties while completing the task?
What was the problem?

D.3 Overall Comments

D.4 General Results

